

Actas de la Reunión Internacional de Expertos sobre la extracción y conservación del pecio *Mazarrón 2*

Proceedings of the International Experts' Meeting
on the extraction and conservation of the wreck
Mazarrón 2

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Coordinadoras:

Marta Arcos García

Rocío Castillo Belinchón

Celia Cantero Escribano

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A comparative study of conservation methods for waterlogged wood - a review of the 'Cutaway' project

Ingrid Stelzner

Leibniz-Zentrum für Archäologie, Mainz
ingrid.stelzner@leiza.de

Jörg Stelzner

Leibniz-Zentrum für Archäologie, Mainz
joerg.stelzner@leiza.de

Jorge Martinez-Garcia

Lucerne University of Applied Sciences and Arts, School for Engineering and Architecture,
Competence Center Thermal Energy Storage
jorge.martinezgarcia@hslu.ch

Damian Gwerder

Lucerne University of Applied Sciences and Arts, School for Engineering and Architecture,
Competence Center Thermal Energy Storage
damian.gwerder01@hslu.ch

Markus Wittköpper

Leibniz-Zentrum für Archäologie, Mainz
markus.wittkoepper@leiza.de

Waldemar Muskalla

Leibniz-Zentrum für Archäologie, Mainz
mail@waldemuskalla.de

Anja Cramer

Leibniz-Zentrum für Archäologie, Mainz
anja.cramer@leiza.de

Guido Heinz

Leibniz-Zentrum für Archäologie, Mainz
guido.heinz@leiza.de

Elias Hamann

Karlsruher Institut für Technologie, Karlsruhe
elias.hamann@kit.edu

Marcus Zuber

Karlsruher Institut für Technologie, Karlsruhe
markus.zuber@kit.edu

Markus Egg

Leibniz-Zentrum für Archäologie, Mainz
markus.egg@leiza.de

Philipp Schuetz

Lucerne University of Applied Sciences and Arts, School for Engineering and Architecture,
Competence Center Thermal Energy Storage
philipp.schuetz@hslu.ch

Abstract: Wood degrades during the storage in the ground. Depending on its state of preservation and species, archaeological wood will deform, collapse and shrink after excavation. This paper reviews conservation methods used to preserve waterlogged archaeological wood. In the short history of conservation science, various methods have been established. At the Leibniz-Zentrum für Archäologie, a reference collection has been built up considering conservation methods such as alcohol-ether resin, melamine formaldehyde (Kauramin 800®), lactitol/trehalose, polyethylene glycol impregnation with different molecular size followed by freeze-drying, saccharose and silicone oil. The project “Cutaway – Conservation and wood analyses” aimed to compare the treatments and therefore, samples of the reference collection were analysed using structured-light 3D scanning, X-ray and synchrotron micro-computed tomography, light microscopy and scanning electron microscopy. The paper discusses the ability of these methods to prevent shrinkage, collapse and cracking. In addition, the interaction of the consolidant within the microstructure of the wood and the condition of the cell walls is assessed.

Keywords: Waterlogged wood, conservation methods, comparative analyses, microscopy, X-ray micro-computed tomography.

Resumen: La madera se degrada. Dependiendo de su estado de conservación y de la especie a la que pertenezca, la madera arqueológica se deforma, colapsa y encoge tras la excavación. En este artículo se examinan los métodos de conservación utilizados para preservar la madera arqueológica anegada. En la breve historia de la ciencia de la conservación se han establecido diversos métodos: en el Leibniz-Zentrum für Archäologie se ha creado una colección de referencia en la que se han implementado diversos métodos de conservación como la resina de alcohol-éter, el formaldehído melamínico (Kauramin 800®), el lactitol/trehalosa, la impregnación con polietilenglicol de diferente tamaño molecular seguida de liofilización, la sacarosa y el aceite de silicona. El proyecto «Cutaway - Conservación y análisis de la madera» tenía como objetivo comparar estos tratamientos y, para ello, se analizaron muestras de dicha colección mediante cribado 3D con luz estructurada, tomografía microcomputada de rayos X y sincrotrón, microscopía óptica y microscopía electrónica de barrido. El artículo analiza la capacidad de estos métodos para prevenir la contracción, el colapso y el agrietamiento de la madera anegada. Además, se evalúa la interacción del consolidante en la microestructura de la madera y el estado de las paredes celulares.

Palabras clave: madera anegada, métodos de conservación, análisis comparativos, microscopía, tomografía microcomputada de rayos X.

1. Introduction

Wooden objects are rarely found in archaeological contexts. In temperate climates, the material is mainly preserved in water-saturated, low-oxygen conditions. Degradation takes place from the outside in (Christensen, 1951), with the initial decomposition of easily degradable components such as hemicellulose and cellulose. What remains is mainly a skeleton of lignin, which is difficult to degrade and, if at all, only serves as a nutrient for very specialised microorganisms under these conditions (Björdal, 2012; Pedersen, Łucejko, Modugno *et al.*, 2021). The water surrounding the wooden objects fills the voids and stabilises the structure. Degradation under anaerobic conditions is very slow, so wooden objects can be preserved for thousands of years (Singh, Kim and Chavan, 2022). In contrast, an archaeological wooden artefact will decay within hours of excavation if no precautions are taken.

Depending on the type of wood and the degree of degradation, the three dimensional (3D) structure will change beyond recognition if left to dry uncontrollably (Barbour and Leney, 1981;

Grattan, 1987; Hawley, 1931). This is caused by the collapse of cell cavities or lumina and shrinkage of cell walls. The former is caused by capillary tension and drying stress in the first phase of drying above fibre saturation, while the latter occurs when bound water evaporates below fibre saturation.

Once excavated, wet wood artefacts require stabilising conservation measures to bring them into a stable, dry state and preserve them permanently. These conservation measures correspond to all safeguards and measures aimed at preserving the cultural heritage while respecting its significance, including accessibility for present and future generations (EN 15898:2011).

Since the mid-19th century, appropriate conservation methods have been sought to preserve decaying wooden artefacts (Christensen, 1970). Over time, treatments based on a wide variety of materials and methods have become established. Several comprehensive studies have compared the treatments (Bräker and Bill, 1979; Wittköpper, Muskalla, Brather *et al.*, 2016; www.rgzm.de/kur, 2022) but did not consider the internal structure of the entire sample.

A multitechnique and multiscale comparative study was therefore carried out to clarify which conservation methods for waterlogged archaeological wood can prevent the damage described for untreated air-dried wood, such as cell collapse, shrinkage and cracking, and how the methods stabilise the wood cells. This has been done as part of the research project `Cutaway – Conservation and wood analyses` (2019-2023) where the methods alcohol-ether resin, melamine formaldehyde (Kauramin 800®), lactitol/trehalose, impregnation with aqueous solutions of polyethylene glycol with different molecular weight prior to freeze-drying, saccharose and silicone oil were compared.

The aim of this paper is to present the results in the context of current knowledge. Therefore, a brief overview of the samples and methods that were used in the project is given and references are provided for more detailed information. The main focus is on the discussion of the conservation methods, where, in addition to their background and properties, the main results from the project on the ability to stabilise the wood are discussed with already existing results from literature. Special attention is given to the interaction of the consolidant and the drying method within the wood structure.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. The reference collection at the Leibniz-Zentrum für Archäologie (LEIZA)

During the project «Mass Finds in Archaeological Collections», funded by the German «Kulturstiftung des Bundes und der Länder» (2008-2011) and coordinated by the Leibniz-Zentrum für Archäologie (formerly Römisch-Germanisches Zentralmuseum) and the Archäologische Staatssammlung München, a reference collection was established (Wittköpper, Muskalla, Brather *et al.*, 2016; www.rgzm.de/kur, 2022). This collection consists of 31 test series on seven different wood species. After documentation and analysis of the state of preservation, the approximately 800 specimens were conserved by various cooperation partners including the methods alcohol-ether resin, melamine formaldehyde (Kauramin 800®), lactitol/trehalose, polyethylene glycol with different molecular weight followed by freeze-drying, silicone oil and saccharose (Table 1, («www.rgzm.de/kur,» 2022)). For the purposes of the Cutaway project, 83 samples were selected for further analysis. Therefore, the 10 series were selected which cover most of the preservation methods. From each series, only one out of five samples was selected for each conservation method. The criterion was the sample with the mean shrinkage before and after conservation, measured by 3D structured light scanning. For the microscopic examinations, the coniferous P11/V03 series was selected characterized by a simple and regular structure and reflecting the majority of conservation methods. Core samples of 5 mm diameter were taken with an increment borer from both the degraded outer area and the less degraded core.

Table 1
Brief protocol on the conservation methods investigated

Conservation methods	Institutions and Short Descriptions of the Methods	
Air dried reference (Air)	Institution:	Leibniz-Zentrum für Archäologie, Mainz, Germany
	Treatment:	none, air-drying
	Impregnation solution:	none
Alcohol-ether-resin (AlEt)	Institution:	Schweizerisches Nationalmuseum, Zürich, Switzerland.
	Treatment:	Exchange of water with ethanol. Exchange of ethanol with diethyl ether. Soaking of wood with diethyl ether in resin-diethyl solution. Drying by evaporation of the diethyl ether in the vacuum vessel. Application of surface protection 3% Paraloid B72 solution in acetone.
	Impregnation solution:	70.7% diethyl ether, 16.1% dammar resin, 6.4% rosin, 3.2% dienol D102, 3.2% rhizinus oil, 0.4% PEG 400
Melamine formaldehyde Kauramin 800® (K800)	Institution:	Leibniz-Zentrum für Archäologie, Mainz, Germany
	Treatment:	Soaking in demineralized water. Bath impregnation at room temperature. Replacement of the solution when early polycondensation occurs. Curing of the impregnated wood in the heating cabinet at 60 °C. Afterwards slow, controlled air-drying. Dip in linseed oil varnish.
	Impregnation solution:	25% Kauramin 800® solution (72 L resin + 210 L deionised water, 3.6 L urea, 7.2 L triethylene glycol)
Lactitol-trehalose (LaTr)	Institution:	Brandenburgisches Landesamt für Denkmalpflege, Zossen, Germany
	Treatment:	Starting with 30% concentration. Increasing monthly in 10% steps up to 70%. Bath temperature 55 °C. After removal from the bath, the surfaces were dusted with crystalline lactitol monohydrate and dried in a heating oven over a period of one week. After drying, the surface was cleaned by dabbing with damp cloths.
	Impregnation solution:	lactitol-trehalose solution (9:1) 30%–70%. Addition of biocide if necessary (0,1% Bioban 404)
Polyethylene glycol (PEG 2000) one-step and freeze-drying (PEG1)	Institution:	Nationalmuseet, Copenhagen, Denmark
	Treatment:	Starting with 10% PEG 2000 solution. Increasing the concentration up to 40% at room temperature. Freeze-drying in cooled chamber (approx. –30 °C). Removal of excess PEG from the surface with a soft brush and ethanol. Subsequent surface stabilisation with 25% PEG 2000 solution in ethanol.
	Impregnation solution:	PEG 2000, 10–40% solution with tap water
Polyethylene glycol (PEG 400 and 4000) two-step and freeze-drying (PEG2)	Institution:	Brandenburgisches Landesamt für Denkmalpflege, Zossen, Germany
	Treatment:	Soaking in demineralised water. Starting with 5% PEG 400 solution. Raising the concentration in 5% steps every 4 weeks. At its calculated final concentration, it was kept constant. Then the increase of PEG 4000 solution was continued in 5% steps up to its final concentration where it was kept for 10 weeks. Precooling of the wood to 5 °C then deep-freezing to –25 to –35 °C, freeze-drying in cooled chamber (approx. –30 °C).
	Impregnation solution:	PEG-solution in demineralised water (PEG 400 and PEG 4000) was adapted according to the condition of the wood (PEGcon): 35% PEG solution (of which 10% PEG 400 and 25% PEG 4000) in demineralized water, impregnation at room temperature
Polyethylene glycol (PEG 400, 1500 and 4000) three-step and freeze-drying (PEG3)	Institution:	Archäologische Staatssammlung, Munich, Germany
	Treatment:	Soaking in demineralised water. Starting with 11% increasing to 15% PEG 400 solution at room temperature. 16% increasing to 20.5% PEG 1500 solution at 40 °C. 20.5% increasing to 27.5% PEG 4000 solution at 40 °C. Washing of the wood and wrapping in cellulose tissues. Intermediate storage in freezer (–25 to –35 °C) until freeze-drying. Subsequent freeze-drying in a cooled chamber (approx. –30 °C). Excess of PEG was removed with a brush and ethanol.
	Impregnation solution:	PEG-solution in demineralised water: 15% PEG 400, 20.5% PEG 1500, 27.5% PEG 4000
Saccharose (Sac)	Institution:	Sächsisches Landesamt für Archäologie, Dresden, Germany
	Treatment:	Concentrated the solution in 10% steps, from 10% up to 60% sugar solution at room temperature. Slow, controlled air-drying in microperforated bags. Removal of crystallised sugar residues from the surface with damp sponge.
	Impregnation solution:	Aqueous saccharose solution 10% – 60%. If necessary biocide addition composed of 0.6%, sodium benzoate (E211), 0.5% Parmetol K40, 0.5% Quartasept Plus and 0.02% Tallofin OT
Silicone oil (Sil)	Institution:	Texas University, Texas, USA
	Treatment:	Exchange of water with ethanol. Exchange of ethanol with acetone. Placing the still dripping wet acetone-impregnated samples in impregnation solution under normal atmospheric conditions. Triggering the polymerisation of the impregnation solution by gaseous catalyst: DBTDA (dibutyl diacetate).
	Impregnation solution:	80% silicone oil (SFD1 (66%) + SFD5 (34%) —silanol functional polydimethylsiloxanes •PDMS•) and 20% crosslinker MTMS (methyltrimethoxysilane)

2.2. Methods

The volume of the samples was documented both with structured-light scanning and X-ray micro-computed tomography (μ CT) (Stelzner, Stelzner, Martinez-Garcia *et al.*, 2022). Starting in 2008, the wet samples were scanned with a structured-light 3D scanner (GOM, Metrology, a company of the ZEISS Group) prior to conservation and in the dry state after conservation (Figure 1). To analyse volume changes after approximately ten years, the conserved samples were scanned again in 2020. In addition, the samples were analysed at Lucerne University of Applied Sciences and Arts using μ CT (diondo d2 Germany, Figure 1). To obtain information on the surface and volume of the samples measured by μ CT, the data were analysed using VGStudio Max 3.4 (Volume Graphics, Heidelberg).

The evaluation of the conservation methods was done by determining the dimensional stability based on the volume data derived from the measurements (Stelzner, Stelzner, Martinez-Garcia *et al.*, 2023; Stelzner, Stelzner, Martinez-Garcia *et al.*, 2022). From this the shrinkage (S) of the volume derived from the structured-light 3D scanning of the samples before (V_{wet}) and after (V_{dry}) conservation was calculated (Rowell and Youngs, 1981; Stamm, 1974). To quantify the loss of internal volume due to collapse and cracks, shrinkage was calculated from the volume of the 3D structured light scanning after conservation (V_{dry}) and the volume of the μ CT data (V_{CT}), respectively.

The core samples were split into several parts (Stelzner, Stelzner, Gwerder *et al.*, 2023). The small core samples were analysed with synchrotron μ CT at Karlsruher Institut für Technologie (KIT) to achieve a high resolution (Stelzner, Stelzner, Hamann *et al.*, 2023). Therefore, no further preparation was necessary (Stelzner and Million, 2015). Another set of samples was ground and polished for examination in the Axioscop A1 light microscope (Carl Zeiss GmbH, Jena). For analysis in the scanning electron microscope (SEM, Evo 60, Carl Zeiss GmbH, Jena) the samples were coated with gold (Stelzner, Stelzner, Gwerder *et al.*, 2023).

Figure 1. Overview over samples and measuring design.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Alcohol-ether resin

Background

In addition to experiments on solvent drying, B. Christensen at the Danish National Museum in Copenhagen published the alcohol-ether method (Christensen, 1951), in which the water in the wood structure is gradually replaced by the solvent ethanol, which is then replaced by ether. In the final stage, the find is soaked in dammar resin dissolved in ether and then dried in under vacuum. The high safety risk associated with handling large quantities of highly volatile solvents such as diethyl ether makes the method expensive and difficult to use. Christensen describes the development of strain during drying, which often results in warping, transverse cracks and fissures (Christensen, 1970). In addition, the objects are brittle, fragile and poorly porous, and consolidation or coating is essential. He also emphasises the aesthetic appearance of the objects.

Around 1953, a modified method was introduced at the Swiss National Museum in Zürich (Christensen, 1970), in which rosin, stand oil, oil varnish and castor oil were used in addition to dammar resin (Christensen, 1971; Kramer, 1979; Kramer and Mühlethaler, 1968). Due to the good results, it is still used today, even for fragile objects that have been extracted in their sediment at the Swiss National Museum in Zurich (Schmidt-Ott, André and Bader, 2022). Examination of the forty-year-old objects revealed that most were stable, but some were brittle and some had cracked. However, the brittleness and cracking could not be related to light ageing or changes in relative humidity. Modifications to the resin mixture are currently being tested to optimise the long-term stability of the method (Schmidt-Ott, André, Liengme *et al.*, 2023).

Volume stability

The samples from the collection at the LEIZA conserved with the alcohol-ether resin show very good volume stabilisation (cf. Figure 2, 3b). This is achieved by the solvent drying process. The low shrinkage corresponds to the low capillary forces resulting from the evaporating liquid (Christensen, 1970). Considering the internal structures derived from the μ CT data, the method also shows good stability (cf. Figure 2). Analysis of the μ CT data showed that there was little collapse or cracking inside the specimens.

This positive assessment is also confirmed by previous studies (Bräker, Schoch and Schweingruber, 1979; Schmidt-Ott, André, Liengme *et al.*, 2023), especially for deciduous woods (Mühlethaler, 1973). The scans after 10 years show consistently good values for volume stability.

Interaction within the wood structure

Due to the rather low concentration of the consolidant (cf. Table 1), the sample is light and porous and not strongly affected by the consolidant (cf. Figure 3b, 4, 5b, 6b). These observations are also reported by Christensen (Christensen, 1970).

Under the light microscope the differences between the degradation levels are observed (cf. Figure 4b): The cell walls of the tracheids in the latewood of the inner, well preserved areas seem to be well stabilised. In contrast, the wood structure in the outer, highly degraded area is barely visible. In the latewood, the degraded S2 layers of the fibrous tracheids are partially visible. In SEM analyses, it is observed that the highly degraded secondary cell walls are still in shape, although shrunken and detached from the compound middle lamella (cf. Figure 6b). Small gaps are also visible in the synchrotron data between the compound middle lamella and the secondary cell wall, indicating shrinkage of the secondary cell wall (cf. Figure 5b). These observations confirm previous results (Bräker, Schoch and Schweingruber, 1979, Kramer and Mühlethaler, 1968).

Deposits were seen on the cell walls of the early wood and in some isolated lumen in the latewood (cf. Figure 4b and 5b). These deposits could be considered as consolidants, but a clear identification was not possible. However, it does not appear that the gaps between the composite middle lamella and the secondary cell walls were filled with the consolidant (cf. Figure 6b).

Figure 2. Average volume loss of 83 samples by conservation method (reference air, alcohol-ether resin (AlEt), melamine resin Kauramin 800® (K800), lactitol/trehalose (LaTr), PEG 2000 (PEG1), PEG 400, 4000 (PEG2), PEG 400, 1500, 4000 (PEG3), saccharose (Sac), silicone oil (Sil)). Volume loss was calculated using volume data from measurements of the samples before and after conservation and ten years after conservation using structured-light 3D scanning and μ CT.

Figure 3. Cross-section from μ CT data from sample series Pi1/V03. (a) reference, (b) alcohol-ether resin, (c) melamine resin Kauramin 800®, (d) lactitol/trehalose, (e) PEG 2000, freeze-drying (f) PEG 400, 4000, freeze-drying (g) PEG 400, 1500, 4000, freeze-drying (h) saccharose, (i) silicone oil.

Figure 4. Light microscopy of the sample series Pi/V03 from the low and high degraded area, late and early wood.

Figure 5. Synchrotron μ CT of the sample series Pi/V03 from the high degraded area of the sample, late and early wood (a) reference, (b) alcohol-ether resin, (c) melamine resin Kauramin 800®, (d) lactitol/trehalose, (e) PEG 2000, freeze-drying (f) PEG 400, 4000, freeze-drying (g) PEG 400, 1500, 4000, freeze-drying (h) saccharose, (i) silicone oil.

Figure 6. Scanning electron microscopy of the sample series Pi/V03 from the high degraded part, late wood (a) reference, (b) alcohol-ether resin, (c) melamine resin Kauramin 800®, (d) lactitol/trehalose, (e) PEG 2000, freeze-drying (f) PEG 400, 4000, freeze-drying (g) PEG 400, 1500, 4000, freeze-drying, (h) saccharose, (i) silicone oil.

3.2. Melamin resin Kauramin 800®

Background

As early as the 1930s, attempts were made to preserve wet wood with urea-formaldehyde condensation resins, but these were not pursued further (Bill and Mühlethaler, 1979). In 1959/60, Müller-Beck and Haas (Müller-Beck and Haas, 1960 and 1959) published on the conservation of wet wood using Arigal C, a melamine resin manufactured by Ciba. In this process, the artefacts were soaked in the dissolved precondensate Arigal C, to which a catalyst was added, and irreversibly cross-linked by polycondensation in a heating oven. When Arigal C was no longer available, Ciba-Geigy offered Lyofix 4036 (Lyofix DML) as an alternative. After conservation, a coating of a polyvinyl acetate solution was applied (Ebert, 1977). Haas describes the production of melamine formaldehyde precondensates and experiments with Lyofix DML (Pfersee Augsburg) due to production bottlenecks (Haas, 1985). However, the finds preserved with Arigal or Lyofix showed many transverse cracks. In addition, due to the rapid hardening of the resin, precipitates of the resin were visible on the surface which were difficult to remove (Haas, Müller-Beck, Schweingruber., 1961).

At the Römisch-Germanisches Zentralmuseum in Mainz (RGZM), which has had experience in the conservation of wet wood with melamine/amino resins since 1963, the method was modified in the early 1990s on the initiative of A. Kramer and scientists from BASF, and in 1998 Wittköpper published the result as «Kauramin Tränkharz® CE 5549 liquid» (Wittköpper, 1998). The innovation was to extend the life of the impregnating bath to «prevent spontaneous resin precipitation on the surface». In addition, the amino resin was made more flexible by modification with ethylene glycol, which should prevent the tendency to form transverse cracks. Because of its good dimensional stability, the resin is still used at the Leibniz-Zentrum für Archäologie today under the name Kauramin 800®. Due to the light colour of the wood after preservation, varnishes such as waxes, synthetic resins or oils are used to improve the aesthetic appearance of the wood (Wittköpper, 1998).

Initially, low molecular weight prepolymers (oligomers) are used. These are dissolved in water and allowed to diffuse into the wood. The pH of the treatment is generally adjusted to pH 8.5 using triethanolamine (TEA). However, care must be taken with treatment baths as acidic pH can often catalyse polymerisation before penetration into the wood is complete. Therefore, it is necessary to monitor the pH and turbidity of the solution during treatment to prevent early onset of polymerisation (Kiliç and Kiliç, 2019; Walsh-Korb and Avérous, 2019). Melamine formaldehyde is a thermosetting aminoplast prepared by condensation reactions. After treatment, a rigid 3D polymer network is formed within the wood. One of the main disadvantages of working with melamine formaldehyde resin is the health impact of formaldehyde evaporation into the air (Walsh-Korb and Avérous, 2019).

Currently, this method has also been used, for example, to conserve the shipwrecks found during the construction of the Marmaray project in the Yenikapi district of Istanbul (Kocabaş, Özsait-Kocabaş and Kılıç, 2012) or a 2nd century BC log boat (Kavkler, 2023). Due to the low water absorption of wood conserved with melamine formaldehyde (Kauramin 800®) and coated with linseed oil varnish, the presentation of the oldest log boat in Switzerland in an open-air display was realised due to the low water absorption (Moll-Dau, Klügl and Wittköpper, 2022).

Volume stability

In this study, very good results were obtained with melamine formaldehyde (Kauramin 800®, cf. Figure 2). In the long term, the volume stability of Kauramin 800® is guaranteed. According to the μ CT data, the positive results could be confirmed by a small volume loss in the structure. However, some samples conserved with Kauramin 800® show cell collapse and cracking (cf. Figure 3c). This could be related to samples which have two different states of degradation (Stelzner, Stelzner, Martinez-Garcia *et al.*, 2022). This damage may be due to the stiffness of the resin, which has been criticised in the literature in relation to previous methods using melamine resins (Hug, 1979). It has also been described that Kauramin 800® stabilises highly degraded wood very well, whereas well preserved wood is less stabilised. It was hypothesised that this may be due to poorer penetration of the amino resin prepolymer (Hoffmann, 2009), resulting in collapse and shrinkage of the well-preserved wood.

Interaction within the wood structure

Images of the microstructure of the sample (Pi1-K800/V03-45) conserved with the melamine formaldehyde Kauramin 800® are shown in Figure 4c, 5c, 6c. As a relatively low concentration of 25% resin is used, the lumen is largely empty, resulting in a relatively light weight. This observation confirms earlier analyses where the melamine resin Arigal C was found to precipitate in the secondary cell wall (Haas, Müller-Beck and Schweingruber, 1961). The microscopic analyses show that the melamine formaldehyde Kauramin 800® seems to stabilise both the sound and degraded tracheids (cf. Figure 4c). However, the cell walls of the well-preserved areas appear to be lighter and thinner and therefore less stabilised. In addition, the sample taken from the well-preserved area shows little deformation.

The conservation method performed well in consolidating highly degraded tracheids (cf. Figure 4c, 5c, 6c). The consolidant may have accumulated there to a considerable extent, coating and strengthening the residual cell wall (cf. Figure 6c).

The observations are consistent with the analyses of Spinella *et al.*, who investigated the interaction of melamine formaldehyde in the wood structure using solid-state NMR (Spinella, Chillura Martino, Saladino *et al.*, 2021). They found a much higher proportion in the more degraded surface layers and a lower concentration in the deeper, less degraded layers. They suggested an interaction between the aromatic rings of lignin and the 1,3,5-triazine ring of Kauramin 800®, and the presence of a network of hydrogen bonds involving the consolidant and both components of wood cellulose and lignin. Further studies showed that the melamine formaldehyde resin fills the interstices between

the wood polymers and interacts with them (Altgen, Awais, Altgen *et al.*, 2020). By interacting with the cell wall, the absorption of liquid water and water vapour into the cell wall is reduced. This also limits dimensional changes in the wood.

3.3. Lactitol-Trehalose

Background

Imazu and Morgós published the use of Lactitol MC for the conservation of waterlogged wood (Imazu and Morgos, 1997). An ASE of 99% was obtained for coniferous woods where concentrations of 70% Lactitol MC were used. For hardwood, slightly higher concentrations of about 89% were used. Thus, the dimensional stability of Lactitol MC was higher than that of saccharose. The economy and dimensional stability (ASE 95-98%) of an approximately 700-year-old Japanese umbrella fir coffin ($U_{max} = 400$ to 200%) treated with Lactitol MC was also demonstrated (Imazu and Morgos, 1999). Due to its galactose content, Lactitol MC is more resistant to many microorganisms than saccharose and is not hygroscopic (Imazu and Morgos, 1997). However, the addition of a biocide is still required (Brather, Hoffman and Straetkvern., 2018).

When an aqueous solution of Lactitol MC is dried, three different types of crystals are formed: Lactitol monohydrate, dihydrate and trihydrate. The formation of Lactitol MC trihydrate, which precipitates on the surface as a white foam, is accompanied by an increase in volume, which can cause cracks to form in the object. The damage to highly degraded wood is highlighted by Imazu *et al.* (Imazu, Ito, Fujita *et al.*, 2016). Therefore, the final concentration of the bath solution should reach 85% and the objects should be dried above 50°C to form lactitol MC monohydrate (Imazu and Morgos, 1997; Imazu and Morgos, 2002). Trehalose is also used to prevent trihydrate formation. The addition of trehalose results in lower concentrations of lactitol being required ($T < 50^{\circ}\text{C}$; $c < 85\%$). The solubility of Lactitol MC is increased by the addition of trehalose (Imazu and Morgós, 2002), allowing drying at room temperature (Imazu, Ito, Fujita *et al.*, 2016). Excellent results are also reported for preservation with trehalose alone (Imazu, Ito, Fujita *et al.*, 2016; Kennedy and Pennington, 2014). This method was used to consolidate different type of waterlogged archaeological plant materials (Ito, Kobayashi, Fujita *et al.*, 2023)

Volume stability

In this study, the samples lost considerably amount of their volume immediately after conservation (cf. Figure 2, 3d). The volume remained more or less constant over the long term of ten years. The internal structure based on the μCT of the lactitol/trehalose impregnated samples confirms a poor volume stabilisation. There are examples where the interior of the sample has collapsed considerably. The stabilisation of highly degraded wood is problematic (Hoffmann, 2013; Wevers, 2005).

Interaction within the wood structure

The microstructure of the lactitol/trehalose treated pine sample (Pi1LaTr) is shown in Figures 4d, 5d, 6d. The inhomogeneity was particularly evident in the highly degraded areas: The lumen of the late wood tracheids is filled with the mixture of lactitol and trehalose. In contrast, the lumen of early wood tracheids are largely empty. This may be due to the relatively high concentration of the impregnation solution (70%). Wevers suggests that during air-drying, the consolidant is redistributed and there is a tendency to form a shell at the outside of the wood (Wevers, 2005). In addition, stabilised tracheids were observed in the highly degraded sample, where the cell walls of the earlywood are well defined and remarkably thick. In contrast, non-stabilised tracheids were observed in the core sample taken from the well-preserved area (cf. Figure 4d and 5d). The consolidants are deposited on the degraded cell wall and appear to strengthen it significantly (cf. Figure 6d). However, many cracks are evident, indicating the brittleness of the consolidant, which shows a crystal-like structure adhering to the cell wall.

3.4. Polyethylene glycol

Background

The use of polyethylene glycol (PEG), a type of water-soluble wax, to preserve recent wood was described in Sweden and the USA as early as 1948/49 (Grattan and Clark, 1987). Only a few years later, Stamm mentioned the possibility of treating archaeological wet wood with PEG. Rosenqvist and Organ independently described the use of PEG in 1959, achieving good mould stabilisation (Organ, 1959; Rosenqvist, 1959a and 1959a). Entire ships have been preserved using this method. The most prominent example is the Swedish Vasa, the battleship of King Gustav Adolf II, which sank on its maiden voyage in 1628 and was not raised until 1961. It took 27 years to conserve, dry and restore the Vasa before it was exhibited in 1988 (Elding, 2012). Large-scale projects, such as the conservation of the Viking ship found in Skudelev, Denmark, in 1962, improved techniques and knowledge of conservation methods by adjusting the chain length of PEG molecules to the degree of degradation (Jensen, Petersen and Strætkvern, 2011). The two-stage impregnation was developed by P. Hoffmann during the conservation of the Bremen cog, whose wood has different degrees of degradation (Hoffmann, 2013 and 1986). The use of low molecular weight (LMW) PEG in the first impregnation aims to stabilise the intact cell walls of the well-preserved wood core. Subsequently, high molecular weight (HMW) PEG was used to preserve the severely degraded areas where only fragmentary cell walls are present. This method is still used today to preserve large wooden objects.

The use of freeze-drying of archaeological finds was probably first carried out in the mid-1950s in the Netherlands, the Soviet Union, Denmark, England and Switzerland (Ambrose, 1990). Initially, the material was freeze-dried without prior impregnation. The increase in water volume during freezing caused the find material to become damaged, dry and brittle (Ambrose, 1990; Jones and Eaton, 2006; Organ, 1959).

Freeze-drying is based on first freezing the impregnated object. By reducing the pressure in the lyophilisation unit, sublimation of the gaseous water from the structure takes place. In the freeze dryer, the water re-sublimates as ice on a cooled condenser. This avoids the liquid phase in the object where surface tensions occur. However, the increase in water volume during freezing damages the find material, making it very dry and brittle (Ambrose, 1990; Organ, 1959). Christensen (Christensen, 1971) found a way to avoid this damage by using the freeze-drying process in combination with the solvent tertiary butyl alcohol. The advantage of using organic solvents is that they freeze and sublime easily. The disadvantage is the explosiveness and residual solvent content in the freeze-dried matrix. A. Rosenqvist (Rosenqvist, 1959b) described the process on the Oseberg finds. In the 1960s, archaeological wet wood finds from Papua New Guinea were first impregnated with low molecular weight PEG and then freeze-dried (Ambrose, 1990). The LMW PEG acts as a cryoprotectant and reduces the expansion of water during freezing. As early as 1978, Elmer (1979) described the advantages of the freeze-drying method, such as economy, reliability and reversibility, in the comparative trials on wet wood conservation in Switzerland.

In their research, Cook and Grattan (Cook and Grattan, 1991) combined LMW and HMW PEG with lyophilisation to match the amount of PEG used to the degree of degradation and the species of specimen. A distinction is made between lumen-filling methods and cell wall swelling, or bulking. The low molecular weight PEG acts as a cryoprotectant and prevents water from expanding during freezing. In their research, Cook and Grattan (Cook and Grattan, 1991) combined low and high molecular weight PEGs with lyophilization to match the amount of PEG used to the degree of degradation and the type of wood found. This method is now widely used and gives good results (Harvie, 2023).

Freezing creates a framework of consolidant surrounded by water. Freeze-drying removes the water, leaving the framework of the consolidant in place, stabilising the find. Because the water has

been removed from the find, it is much lighter than in its water-saturated state. Regarding the technical requirements for freeze-drying wetland finds, Hoffmann *et al.* (Hoffmann, Riens and Eckstein, 1991) describe comparative studies on the drying of wooden artefacts. Due to the increased radiant heat and the lack of water vapour removal, freeze-drying with a cooled recipient is recommended (Hoffmann, Riens and Eckstein, 1991; Jensen, Strætkvern, Schnell *et al.*, 2009).

The disadvantage of using hygroscopic low molecular weight polyethylene glycol is that the melting point of the aqueous solution cannot be lowered during lyophilisation (Schnell and Jensen, 2007). Furthermore, they are mobile during storage, migrate out of the object and carry an increased risk of degradation reactions after conservation due to their hygroscopicity (Walsh-Korb and Avérous, 2019). Accordingly, only high molecular weight PEG 2000 is usually used for pre-soaking, especially in Scandinavian countries (Harvie, 2023; Jensen, Petersen and Strætkvern, 2011).

Volume stability

Polyethylene glycol (PEG 2000) one-step and freeze-drying

Good volume stabilisation was achieved by impregnation with PEG 2000 and lyophilisation (cf. Figure 2). After 10 years, the samples conserved with PEG 2000 showed consistently high values of volume stability. The internal structure analysed with μ CT data confirmed good volume stability. It is noticeable that samples treated with an aqueous solution of PEG 2000 before freeze-drying show the formation of cracks (cf. Figure 3e). The development of cracks can be explained by the freeze-drying process, where the first step is the freezing of the impregnated wood. The freezing of the aqueous solution in the wood leads to an expansion of its volume, resulting in cracks (Jensen, Jørgensen and Schnell, 2002). PEG-conserved objects have low strength (Bräker, Schoch and Schweingruber, 1979). In addition, the cracks that can form during freezing may increase fragility.

Polyethylene glycol (PEG 400 and 4000) two-step and freeze-drying

A good volume stabilisation was also achieved in the samples conserved in two steps with PEG 400 and PEG 4000 followed by lyophilisation (cf. Figure 2). The volumes of the samples did not change significantly after 10 years.

Considering the internal structures with μ CT, the volume stabilisation inside the samples is good (cf. Figure 3f). The analyses showed the formation of cracks within the samples (Stelzner, Stelzner, Martinez-Garcia *et al.*, 2022). The cracks appear to be less pronounced than in the samples impregnated with one-step or three-step PEG prior to lyophilisation. In addition, a collapsed internal structure can be observed in some samples. This may be due to the low critical temperature of the PEG 400 and 4000 solutions, which may not freeze during freeze-drying (Stelzner, 2018, Jensen, Jørgensen and Schnell, 2002).

Polyethylene glycol (PEG 400, 1500 and 4000) three-step and freeze-drying

Less shrinkage was obtained from the samples conserved in three steps with PEG 400, PEG 1500 and PEG 4000 and then lyophilised (cf. Figure 2). The volume was stable over a period of ten years. The formation of cracks and collapse in the structure was also confirmed (cf. Figure 3g).

Interaction within the wood structure

Polyethylene glycol (PEG 2000) one-step and freeze-drying

The microstructure of the sample impregnated with an aqueous solution of PEG 2000 prior to lyophilisation is shown in Figure 4e, 5e and 6e. The random distribution of PEG in the lumen of the wood tissue, which has a porous structure due to freeze-drying, can be seen in the lumen of

some tracheids (Figure 5e). More PEG is deposited in the highly degraded outer area of the sample than in the less degraded areas (Figure 4e). In the low degraded areas, the cell walls of the latewood tracheids are partially compact, but the degraded secondary cell wall is shrunken and detached from the compound middle lamella. In the severely degraded areas, the cell walls of the earlywood appear very thin (cf. Figure 4e and 5e). There are several areas where the secondary cell wall has degraded and separated from the well-preserved compound middle lamella. However, it appears that some cavities within the cell wall are filled with the PEG (cf. Figure 6e).

Polyethylene glycol (PEG 400 and 4000) two-step and freeze-drying

The microstructure of a sample treated with an aqueous solution of PEG 400 and PEG 4000 is shown in Figure 4f, 5f and 6f. Large inorganic crystals from the burial environment have been incorporated into the wood tissue (cf. Figure 4f). The secondary cell wall shows a high degree of degradation, while the composite middle lamella is well visible. The degraded structure is stabilised by a random distribution of freeze-dried high molecular weight PEG in the lumina (cf. Figure 5f). A higher concentration of PEG was observed in the highly degraded outer areas in the lumen of both early and late wood. Deposits of consolidants are visible in the secondary cell wall of the tracheids (cf. Figure 6f). However, gaps in the cell walls indicate shrinkage of the secondary cell wall.

Polyethylene glycol (PEG 400, 1500 and 4000) three-step and freeze-drying

The microstructure of the sample treated with an aqueous solution containing PEG 400, 1500 and 4000 prior to lyophilisation is shown in Figure 4g, 5g and 6g). The structure is well preserved due to the PEG being deposited in the lumen. In the highly degraded areas, some tracheids do not appear to be stabilised at all, whereas the less degraded tracheids are well preserved (cf. Figure 4g). The degraded cell wall is additionally stabilised by the consolidant, but not completely, leaving gaps between the compound middle lamella and the secondary wall, which may have shrunk (cf. Figure 5g and 6g).

The study showed that, low molecular weight PEG appeared to stabilise the cell walls. PEG of higher molecular weight is also precipitated on the cell walls. High concentrations also fill the lumen. This observation is confirmed by several studies (Bilz, Grant and Young, 1999; Cook and Grattan, 1991; Hoffmann, 1986). During impregnation, PEG penetrates the mesopores of the wood cell wall and replaces the water. This can happen even in sound cell walls, which are penetrated up to a molecular weight of 3000 g/mol (Penttilä, Altgen, Awais *et al.*, 2020). Only a fraction of the PEG interacts with the wood, especially with lignin, resulting in close molecular interaction and mechanical stability (Bardet, Gerbaud, Giffard *et al.*, 2009; Bardet, Gerbaud, Trân *et al.*, 2007).

3.5. Saccharose

Background

Since the publication of Parrent (Parrent, 1985), for example, who achieved acceptable stabilisation results of wet wood, many experiments have been carried out with the inexpensive conservation sucrose (cane sugar) (e.g. (Hoffmann, 1996a; Koesling, 1992). For example, a Bronze Age dugout canoe from Ivera, Italy (Strigazzi, 1997) and the 18-metre-long medieval cargo sailer from Immenstadt on Lake Constance were preserved with normal household sugar. The advantage of the method appeared to lie in the affinity of the sugar to wood, its small molecular size and the associated fast and effective conservation. Sugar conservation is hardly used today. This is because the disaccharide sugar is split into its strongly hygroscopic building blocks glucose and fructose by acid or enzymatic degradation by microorganisms (Schiweck, 1996). The conservation solutions can only be stabilised by massive use of biocides (Mietke and Martin, 1999). For this reason, many conservators today prefer other methods.

Volume stability

The samples conserved with saccharose analysed in this study show a poorer conservation overall (cf. Figure 2) and the results vary greatly which confirms the results from other researchers that found that this method yields less reliable results (Grattan and Clarke, 1987; Hoffmann, 1996a). Figure 3h presents a nicely stabilised structure, however, significant collapse was documented in other samples (Stelzner, Stelzner, Martínez-García *et al.*, 2022). The volume of the saccharose conserved samples revealed good stabilisation over time.

The reason for low stabilisation is not solely related to a low concentration of consolidant. There can also occur problems with highly concentrated solutions. Their susceptibility to degradation by osmotolerant microorganisms can lead to the development of slime and gases, which can prevent consolidants from penetrating the wood. Due to the low penetration of the biocides, fermentation processes cannot be prevented. Saccharose is decomposed by chemical or microbiological processes. It is converted into the monosaccharides of fructose and glucose having lower stabilisation properties. These degradation products are also more hygroscopic leading to a damp surface and poorer drying (Hoffmann, 2010; Mietke and Martin, 1999; Schiweck, 1996).

Interaction within the wood structure

The microstructure of samples treated with saccharose is shown in Figure 4h, 5h and 6h. It is absorbed differently by the structure. Saccharose was deposited predominantly in the latewood tracheids with their small lumen. Partially also the earlywood was filled (cf. Figure 4h and 5h). These findings are confirmed by other studies, where it was observed that saccharose fills most of the tracheids (Hoffmann, 2013) but an uneven uptake of saccharose was suspected (Hoffmann, 1996b). A lower uptake of saccharose was observed in the tylose-containing earlywood vessels was observed (Schmitt and Noldt, 1994). The structure of the tylose cell wall, which contains an inner layer of suberin, a chemically very resistant hydrophobic material is assumed to be the reason. Saccharose accumulates in the small latewood vessels and in the parenchyma cells because the hydroxyl groups of cellulose interact with those of saccharose. Thereby hydroxyl bonds are formed (Broda and Hill, 2021; Parrent, 1985).

The ability of saccharose to fill the wood structure by bulking the vessels, lumina, and cell walls is mentioned in earlier studies (Parrent, 1985). Considerably more saccharose was located in the low degraded area, where the lumen of the earlywood tracheids is filled as well (cf. Figure 4h). The fact that conservation with saccharose is better for well-preserved wood is also mentioned by Hoffmann (Hoffmann, 1996b). It was also found that the uptake of saccharose is dependent on the anatomical direction: the uptake is higher in the tangential direction due to the degradation of the pits and the higher permeability of the solution (Hoffmann, 1994).

Shrinkage of the secondary cell walls of some tracheids was observed, leaving gaps visible between the secondary cell wall and the compound middle lamella (cf. Figure 6h). In the SEM, saccharose is visible covering the residual cell walls and in the lumina which is confirmed by other studies (Hoffmann, Pérez de Andrés, Sierra Méndez *et al.*, 1995).

3.6. Silicone oil

Background

In 1980, Gunter van Hagen patented his work on the consolidation of animal tissue with silicone based polymers (US - US-4205059-A), where he uses both a polymer and a catalyst followed by introduction of a cross linker (Kavvouras, Kostarelou, Zisi *et al.*, 2009). A few years later, in 1996, researchers at Archaeological Preservation Research Laboratory of Texas A&M University experi-

mented got several US patents (US - 5,789,087/ US - 6,022,589/ US - 6,020,027/ US - 6,432,553/ US - 6,835,411) on the treatment of archaeological wood with 'silicon oils' and methyltrimethoxysilane (MTMOS) for wood conservation where the cell walls are impregnated with polymers and cross-linkers followed by the addition of catalyst (Hamilton, 2010; Smith, 2003). The experiments on this method were continued (Kavvouras, Kostarelou, Zisi *et al.*, 2009; Toloczko and Crawshaw, 2023). Further, a lot of research is currently being done on the treatment of silanes and siloxanes (Broda, Spear, Curling *et al.*, 2021; Broda, Dąbek, Dutkiewicz *et al.*, 2020; Broda, Curling, Spear *et al.*, 2019).

Volume stability

The samples in this study were treated with two kinds of silicone oil (SFD1 and SFD5), a crosslinker (methyltrimethoxysilane, MTMS) and a catalyst (dibutyltin diacetate/dibutyltin diacetate, DBDTA) (Table 1). These samples tend to show poorer volume stabilisation overall (cf. Figure 2). These findings are confirmed by former studies (Kavvouras, Kostarelou, Zisi *et al.*, 2009). However, the volume is stable after ten years. The inner structure analysed with μ CT shows varying results (cf. Figure 3i). There are samples where the structure has collapsed (Stelzner, Stelzner, Martinez-Garcia *et al.*, 2022).

Interaction within the wood structure

The microstructure of samples treated with silicone oil is shown in Figure 4i, 5i and 6i showing a well-preserved structure. The uptake of silicone is dependent on the state of localisation/state of degradation of the coresample: more silicone is concentrated in the outer high degraded areas than in the well preserved center of the sample (cf. Figure 3i and 4i). The consolidant is predominantly deposited in the small-lumen latewood where no structural details are visible (cf. Figure 5i). Only to a lower fraction the lumen is filled in the earlywood tracheids. The cell walls are fully saturated with silicone which is seen in the earlywood (cf. Figure 6i). This is due to the high concentration of approximately 100% of the conservation solution (cf. Table 1). The stabilisation is however, dependent of the chemical composition of the organosilicons (Broda, Dąbek, Dutkiewicz *et al.*, 2020). Alkoxysilanes seem to coat the cell walls while siloxanes cover the cell walls but also fill the lumen. Dependent on the amount of MTMS, for example, the surface area and total pore volume is decreasing. A softening effect as well as the reduction of moisture content was observed, which was dependent on the degree of degradation and the type of wood (Broda, Spear, Curling *et al.*, 2021). MTMS bonds with wood polymers via hydrogen or ionic bonds involving amino groups. In addition, Alkoxysilanes can also react not only with the hydroxyl groups of the wood, but also condense with their own molecules. Through these reactions, a potential spatial network is created that stabilizes the structure of the wood (Popescu and Broda, 2021).

4. Conclusion

Waterlogged archaeological wood is degraded during burial. If it is drying after excavation, it will suffer from shrinkage, collapse and cracks. Therefore, conservation measures are prerequisites for the preservation of archaeological objects. In this study, the most frequently used methods were compared by quantifying the damage patterns: shrinkage was evaluated by structured-light 3D scanning before and after conservation and collapse and cracks was analysed using μ CT.

Reliable stabilisation of the surface was achieved with the conservation methods polyethylene glycol (PEG), alcohol-ether resin and melamine formaldehyde Kauramin 800[®]. The other conservation methods caused considerable fluctuations and, in some cases, a large loss of volume. The volume change over 10 years period in uncontrolled museum climate, is considerably reduced through conservation measures (Stelzner, Stelzner, Martinez-Garcia *et al.*, 2022).

For the first time, the internal structure of the sample was considered and the damage patterns collapse and cracks were analysed. Collapse takes place, when liquid phases are forming during drying. The evaporating water causes this type of damage by the development of capillary forces derived from surface tension. This is avoided by the use of solvent drying and freeze-drying. However, liquid phases can also result in collapse in very degraded wood during freeze-drying (Jensen, Jørgensen and Schnell 2002, Schnell and Jensen, 2007; Stelzner, 2018). Moreover, the formation of ice crystals during freezing can result in cracks due to volume expansion of the aqueous solution. It seems that the addition of low molecular weight PEG reduces this effect.

The interaction of the consolidant with the wood matrix was investigated by analysing the microstructure on a series of pine samples with SEM and microscopy and the cross-sectional images from XCT near the same surface (Stelzner, Stelzner, Gwerder *et al.*, 2023). The consolidants could be identified in the structure, with the resins (alcohol-ether resin, melamine resin) mainly in the cell walls, and the PEG and sugars (lactitol/trehalose, saccharose) also in the cell lumina whereas the silicone was seen throughout the wood structure. The distribution of the consolidants seems to be determined by the drying method. In the air-dried samples the consolidants (saccharose and lactitol/trehalose) were mainly deposited in the late wood cells. On the other hand, the freeze-dried PEG matrix was distributed over the entire structure of the sample. Besides drying, wood anatomy and degree of degradation are important factors.

In order to preserve decayed waterlogged wooden archaeological objects, the stabilisation of the surface and the internal structure is essential. In addition, the distribution of the consolidant plays a major role. However, these observations also show that further research and validation of the results are needed. Further studies will analyse the structure of the wet samples before conservation and the sample after conservation as well as the stability of consolidants in museum climates.

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